

SPECIAL ISSUE

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

VOLUME II | ISSUE 3 | MAY-JUNE | 2024

ISSN: 2181-4031

Available online at www.imfaktor.com

ISSN: 2181-4031
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4031

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

II-ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ- II, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

VOLUME-II, ISSUE 3

ТОШКЕНТ – 2024

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ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

№ 3 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.56017/2181-4031-2024-3>

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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11501468>

THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM AND JUSTICE: ADVANCING JUSTICE AND THE RULE OF LAW IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND CENTRAL ASIA

ANNOTATION

This scientific article examines the key role of the courts in ensuring legality, justice and protection of citizens' rights enshrined in the Constitution. The authors analyze judicial processes and institutions of appeal and cassation in the context of legal systems, as well as problems related to their effectiveness and independence. Special attention is paid to the prospects for the development of the judicial system in Central Asia and the factors influencing judicial processes in the region. The article makes a valuable contribution to understanding the judicial system and its role in ensuring legal order and justice in society.

Keywords: courts, human rights, legality, judicial system, appeal, cassation, justice, independence, legal system, Central Asia.

SUD TIZIMI VA ADOLAT: ADOLAT VA QOIDANI RIVOJLANTIRISH O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI VA MARKAZIY OSIYODA QONUNCHILIK

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu ilmiy maqolada Konstitutsiyada mustahkamlangan qonuniylik, adolat va fuqarolarning huquqlarini himoya qilishda sudlarning asosiy roli ko'rib chiqilgan. Mualliflar sud jarayonlari va apellyatsiya va kassatsiya institutlarini huquqiy tizimlar nuqtai nazaridan, shuningdek ularning samaradorligi va mustaqilligi bilan bog'liq muammolarni tahlil qiladilar. Markaziy Osiyoda sud-huquq tizimini rivojlantirish istiqbollari va mintaqadagi sud jarayonlariga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Maqola sud tizimini va uning jamiyatda huquqiy tartib va adolatni ta'minlashdagi rolini tushunishga qimmatli hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sudlar, inson huquqlari, qonuniylik, sud tizimi, apellyatsiya, kassatsiya, adolat, mustaqillik, huquqiy tizim, Markaziy Osiyo.

СУДЕБНАЯ СИСТЕМА И ПРАВОСУДИЕ: УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ СПРАВЕДЛИВОСТИ И ВЕРХОВЕНСТВА ПРАВА ВЕРХОВЕНСТВО ЗАКОНА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН И ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной научной статье рассматривается ключевая роль судов в обеспечении законности, правосудия и защиты прав граждан, закрепленных в Конституции. Авторы анализируют судебные процессы и институты апелляции и кассации в контексте правовых систем, а также проблемы, связанные с их эффективностью и независимостью. Особое внимание уделяется перспективам развития судебной системы в Центральной Азии и факторам, влияющим на судебные процессы в регионе. Статья вносит ценный вклад в понимание судебной системы и ее роли в обеспечении правопорядка и справедливости в обществе.

Ключевые слова: суды, права человека, законность, судебная система, апелляция, кассация, правосудие, независимость, правовая система, Центральная Азия.

THE MAIN PART:

The courts play an important role in strengthening human rights and freedoms enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as in strengthening law and order in society and raising the legal consciousness of the population. Thus, further strengthening the authority of the court, ensuring the full independence of the courts and improving the efficiency of judicial proceedings are important conditions for the further development of our country.

The main priorities of the State policy are aimed at further reforming the judicial and legal system, ensuring the full independence of the judicial system and increasing the effectiveness of judicial, law enforcement and supervisory authorities, increasing public confidence in justice, ensuring the rule of law and strengthening the rule of law in society [1].

In accordance with article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, everyone has the right to defend their rights and freedoms in all ways not prohibited by law. Everyone is guaranteed judicial protection of his rights and freedoms, the right to appeal to the court against illegal decisions, actions and inaction of state bodies and other organizations, their officials.

Significant changes have taken place in the criminal procedure legislation in order to improve its norms and introduce advanced international standards and practices in other countries. The purpose of these changes was to guarantee the unconditional protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens involved in criminal proceedings.

One of the procedural ways to verify the legality and validity of a verdict, ruling and court decision that has entered into force is to review court decisions in higher instances.

The elimination of judicial errors and ensuring the inevitability of punishment through appeal, cassation and supervision are today's urgent tasks, as Akhmadzhanov O. notes. [2, P.151].

According to N.N.Polyansky, the judges considering the case in the first instance know that every sentence and decision they have passed, as well as decisions regarding the order and conditions in which the case was rendered, will be ensured by the interests of justice, knowing that a high instance may become the subject of evaluation [3, P.208].

According to B.A.Mirensky and other academics, a criminal case in cassation can be considered only once, in one court instance [4, P.444]

Theoretically, paying attention to the appeal and cassation systems, two opposing legal systems collided on the territory of Uzbekistan, firstly, Romano-German (continental) law. Cassation proceedings occupy the main place in this legal system. Secondly, the case is on appeal, relating to the Anglo-Saxon legal system. It is obvious that the joint use of institutions belonging to this opposite right will lead to the fact that in the future the courts will steadily increase the volume of criminal cases to be considered, and that legislation and justice will influence as a negative factor for decision-making.

In Uzbekistan, the deadline for filing an appeal is 10 days, while in Kazakhstan, according to the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the deadline for filing appeals and prosecutor's petitions is 15 days from the date of the announcement of the verdict, the resolution, which is equal to the deadline for filing an appeal in Kyrgyzstan.

In Tajikistan, the review of sentences, rulings and resolutions that have not entered into force is carried out in cassation. There, complaints and protests against the court's verdict can be filed by the parties within ten days from the moment the verdict is announced, and if the convicted person is in custody, within the same period from the moment a copy of the verdict is handed to him. In Turkmenistan, too, court verdicts that have not entered into force can be appealed or submitted by the parties to the cassation instance. In Turkmenistan, a complaint and a submission against the verdict of the court of first instance may be brought within ten days from the date of the verdict, and if the convicted person is in custody, the period for appealing the verdict is calculated from the date of handing him a copy of the verdict.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, there is a 3-instance system for reviewing sentences, consisting of appeal, cassation instances and the resumption of criminal proceedings on newly discovered circumstances, while in Uzbekistan there are 5 stages of reviewing a criminal case [5].

In the criminal proceedings of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are restrictions regarding the review of sentences that have entered into force, in cassation. Such restrictions are provided for in Part 2 of Article 484 of the CPC of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

This restriction allows you to relieve the burden of reviewing criminal cases of a certain category and creates obstacles to the mechanical appeal of sentences.

In addition, Part 3 of this article allows, under certain conditions, to review in cassation the judicial acts of local and other courts that have entered into force in case of non-compliance with the appellate procedure for their appeal, as well as the above-mentioned judicial acts.

Also, the Chairman of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Kazakhstan, along with the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Kazakhstan, has the right to submit submissions on the cassation review of judicial acts that have entered into force, both on his own initiative and at the request of interested persons. This possibility is fixed in Article 486 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Kazakhstan establishes restrictions on the appeal of sentences that have entered into force in cassation. Such a condition prevents the mechanical appeal of sentences and allows you to relieve the burden from the courts of cassation instance [6].

CONCLUSION:

The study of judicial review systems in the criminal process of Central Asian countries highlights the importance of the judicial system as a tool for strengthening the rights and freedoms of citizens, maintaining law and order in society, as well as raising the legal awareness of the population. The main priorities of the State policy in this area are aimed at reforming the judicial and legal system, ensuring the independence of the courts and improving the efficiency of judicial proceedings.

The process of reviewing judicial decisions in higher instances plays an important role in ensuring the fairness and validity of sentences, as well as in correcting judicial errors. Restrictions on the appeal of sentences that have entered into force help to relieve the burden on the courts and reduce the mechanical appeal of sentences, which contributes to a more efficient functioning of the judicial system.

The development of the judicial system in accordance with international standards and best practices is a necessary step to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens, strengthen the rule of law and increase public confidence in justice.

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ISSN: 2181-4031
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4031

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ТОМ-II, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

VOLUME-II, ISSUE 3

«Фундаментал тадқиқотлар» электрон журнали 2022 йил 22 декабрь куни № 054837-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

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